

Project DEFINERS – Questionnaire Instrument
Digital Practices and Attitudes of Junior Language Teachers

Administrative details

Version	1.2
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Attribution and peer-review	This questionnaire builds upon and expands the concise statement-based instrument on willingness to communicate (WTC) and Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE) developed by Lee and Sylvén (2021) for their study of Korean and Swedish EFL learners' communication behaviour (<i>British Journal of Educational Technology</i> , 52 (3), 1279–1296; https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13082). The questionnaire also underwent double-blind review by six international experts (Spain × 3, Portugal × 1, China × 1, United States × 1) prior to administration and public release.
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1. Purpose and scope

This structured questionnaire captures demographic data, willingness to communicate, language-mixing attitudes, online reception and production habits, transfer of digital practices into teacher education, and perceived value of digital resources among pre-service and early-career language teachers. It aligns with Project DEFINERS' objective to document how emerging professionals engage with digital tools, social media, and video-game environments for language learning and teaching.

2. Ethical notes for researchers

- Adapt and distribute the informed-consent notes.
- Participation is voluntary, uncompensated, and anonymous; data are stored securely and reported in aggregate.
- Estimated completion time: 12–15 minutes.
- The instrument may be delivered on paper, as a web form, or via compatible survey software.

3. Instrument structure and items

Below is a faithful transcription of the original survey. Where response options repeat across items, the Likert anchors are shown once for brevity.

Section A – Project information & consent

Introductory text explaining project aims, target population, rights, and consent checkbox (“I consent”).

Section B – Demographic data

Item	Question	Response format
B1	What is your sex/gender?	Woman / Man / Other (+open text)
B2	How old are you?	18–23 / 24–29 / 30–35 / 36 +
B3	Field of undergraduate studies	Multiple choice (English Philology, Hispanic Philology, Other, etc.)
B4	Highest degree	Bachelor, Master, PhD, None
B5	Daily hours using non-native languages outside school	<1 h, 1 h, 1–3 h, >3 h
B6	Country of residence	List + “Other (text)”
B7	Lived abroad in a non-L1 country?	Yes < 3 m / Yes 3–6 m / Yes > 6 m / No
B8	Languages known + proficiency	Open grid (Mother tongue, Advanced, Intermediate, Beginner)
B9	Foreign language with most formal study	Open text
B10	Foreign language with most self-directed study	Open text
B11	Language(s) you would like to teach	Single choice

Item	Question	Response format
B12	If in-service, main language you currently teach	Open text
B13	Teaching experience	None / <6 m / 6 m-1 y / 1-3 y / 3-5 y / >5 y

Section C – Willingness to communicate

- C1.** I feel anxious when I have the chance to talk in a formal situation in the language(s) I learn.
- C2.** If I have to give a formal presentation, I feel at ease to communicate in the language(s) I learn.
- C3.** When I chat over social media or video games, I spot and correct the mistakes I make in the language(s) I write.
- C4.** If I have an informal chat with friends, I am willing to communicate in the language(s) I learn.
- C5.** Overall, how willing are you to communicate in the language(s) you learn? *(5-point willingness scale)*
- C6.** (Open) Additional explanation for your answer to C5.

Section D – Language-mixing attitudes

- D1.** I find it unpleasant when people mix languages in daily speech.
- D2.** It is nice when language teachers mix languages during lectures.
- D3.** I find it unpleasant when language learners mix languages in class.
- D4.** It is nice when people mix languages in writing or chats.
- D5.** I find it unpleasant when people mix languages in memes or stickers.
- D6.** Considering the previous answers, rate how pleasant you find seeing/using multiple languages in any communicative situation (*1 = I don't like it at all → 5 = I like it a lot*)
- D7.** (Open) Additional explanation for your answer to D6.

Section E – Online learning – Reception

- E1.** I set my devices to the language(s) I learn to pick up new words.
- E2.** I receive emails in the language(s) I learn about university/professional topics.
- E3.** I read posts, memes, or comments on social media in the language(s) I learn.
- E4.** I listen to podcasts in the language(s) I learn.
- E5.** I watch social-media videos in the language(s) I learn.
- E6.** I use subtitles when I watch online videos...
- ...in **my mother tongue**
 - ...in **the language I learn**
- E7.** I read fan-fiction in the language(s) I learn.
- E8.** Considering the above, rate how much watching/reading online helps you learn language(s) (*1 = Doesn't help at all → 5 = Helps a lot*).
- E9.** (Open) Additional explanation for your answer to E8.

Section F – Online learning – Production

- F1.** I use the autocorrect option when drafting texts in the language(s) I learn.
- F2.** I use a translator to help me draft texts in the language(s) I learn.
- F3.** I post in the language(s) I learn on social media.
- F4.** I reply in the same language(s) when I see posts/comments online.
- F5.** I chat with others in the language(s) I learn via social media.

F6. I create and upload captions/subtitles for videos.

F7. I write and upload fan-fiction in the language(s) I learn.

F8. Considering the above, rate how much chatting/writing/creating online helps you learn language(s) (*1 = Doesn't help at all → 5 = Helps a lot*).

F9. (Open) Additional explanation for your answer to F8.

Section G – Transfer to teacher education

G1. At university, teachers ask me to use social media/video games for learning language(s).

G2. Teachers ask me to use or draw on digital tools/social media/video games to design activities and lessons.

G3. Regardless of teachers, I use digital tools/social media/video games for inspiration on becoming a teacher.

G4. Regardless of teachers, I use digital tools/social media/video games for learning languages.

G5. Name one top social media platform or video game you have used for inspiration in teacher training or classes. (*open*)

G6. How did you discover that platform or game? (*Teacher / Friends / Self-discovery*)

G7. Rate how much attention you think schools pay to...

- Digital tools
- Social media
- Video games

(*1 = Minimal → 5 = A lot of attention*)

Section H – Overall valuation

H1. As a language learner, how beneficial do you find...

- Digital tools
- Social media
- Video games

(*1 = Not beneficial at all → 5 = Very beneficial*)

H2. As a teacher, how beneficial do you rate using those resources in class? (*same anchors*)

H3. Would you like to receive the project results? (*No / Yes + email*)

H4. Would you be willing to participate in an interview? (*No / Yes + email*)

4. Suggested citation text

“This questionnaire is part of Project DEFINERS (TED2021-129984A-I00) investigating digital language-learning practices of preservice and early-career teachers. Your anonymous answers will inform evidence-based teacher-education curricula that leverage digital tools, social media, and gaming platforms.”

Feel free to adapt wording when administering in other contexts or languages.

5. Change log

Date	Version	Notes
15 Dec 2022	1	First draft submitted for peer review.
31 Jan 2023	1.1	Peer-reviewed revision distributed for global administration.
27 May 2025	1.2	Public release on Zenodo.